

Skills 4 eosc

Deliverable 3.6.

Coordinated set of guides, fact-sheets and FAQs on ELSI aspects for Civil Servants and Policy Makers

Lead Partner:	KUL
Version:	V.1 (general issues draft)
Status:	Sumbitted draft not yet approved by the EC
Dissemination Level:	PU: Public
Document Link:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7991444
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.7991444

Deliverable Abstract

In order to contribute with the Training Material from Task 3.1., the Science4Policy Kit from Task 3.3., and the Workshops “The Practice of Informing Policy Through Evidence” from T3.5., this deliverable 3.6. provides training materials in the for of guides, fact-sheets and FAQs on ELSI aspects including but not limited to ethical issues, Intellectual Property Rights, Public Sector Information and Research Data, Licensing, Database Sui Generis Rights, and Personal Data Protection. This first version focuses on general issues and that may be of interest of both civil servants and policy makers, amongst other relevant profiles, like researchers, data stewards and legal and ethical advisors.

Skills4EOOSC has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101058527 and from UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10040140]

COPYRIGHT NOTICE

This work by Parties of the Skills4EOSC Project is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). The Skills4EOSC project is co-funded by the European Union Horizon Europe programme under grant n° 101058527 and by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee under grant n° 10040140.

DELIVERY SLIP

<i>Date</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Partner/Activity</i>	<i>Date</i>
<i>From:</i>	Luca Schirru	KUL	
<i>Moderated by:</i>			
<i>Reviewed by:</i>			
<i>Approved by:</i>			

DOCUMENT LOG

<i>Issue</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Comment</i>	<i>Author</i>
<i>v.0.0</i>	<i>10.02.23</i>	<i>Draft created</i>	<i>Luca Schirru, Valentina Colcelli and Sabrina Brizioli.</i>
<i>V.0.1</i>	<i>14.04.23</i>	<i>Integration of comments by internal reviewers and contributors</i>	<i>Luca Schirru, Valentina Colcelli, Sabrina Brizioli, and Emircan Karabuga. Reviewers: Elora Fernandes (Section on Personal Data Protection) and Thomas Margoni</i>
<i>V1.0</i>	<i>31.05.23</i>	<i>approved</i>	<i>Emma Lazzeri, Sara Di Giorgio (GARR)</i>

TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

<i>Terminology/Acronym</i>	<i>Definition</i>
IPRs	Intellectual Property Rights
InfoSoc	Directive on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyrights and related rights in the information society
DGA	Data Governance Act
DMA	Digital Markets Act
DSA	Digital Services Act
TRIPS	Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights
DA	Data Act (proposal)
ODD	Open Data Directive (Directive 2019/1024)
CDSM	Directive on Copyright and Related Rights in the Digital Single Market (Directive 2019/790)
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation 2016/679)
AIA	Artificial Intelligence Act
WPPT	WIPO Performances and Phonograms Treaty
WCT	WIPO Copyright Treaty

Contents

1	Introduction	5
2	Personal Data Protection	7
2.1	Fact Sheets	7
2.2	FAQ	10
3	Intellectual Property Rights and other non-personal data.	14
3.1	Fact Sheets	14
3.2	FAQ	14
4	Ethics in research and open science	44
4.1	FAIR Principles	45
4.2	Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)	47
4.3	European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity	48
5	References	50
6	Appendix	55

1 Introduction

The main objective of this deliverable is to contribute with the “Open Science training for Policy Makers and Civil Servants” from Task 3.1., the “Science4Policy kit” from Task 3.3. and with the Workshops “The Practice of Informing Policy Through Evidence” from Task 3.5. This contribution will take the form of training materials: guides, fact-sheets and FAQs, as described below:

FAQs on the following topics:

- Personal Data Protection;
- Intellectual property and other non-personal data protection, including the following:
 - Intellectual Property (general aspects);
 - Copyright;
 - Intersection between Copyright and Open Science;
 - Licensing;
 - Sui Generis Database Rights;
 - Trade Secrets;
 - Non-personal data and Public Sector Bodies;
 - Data under the Open Data Directive;
 - Data under the Data Governance Act;
 - Data under EU-Funded Projects.

Fact Sheets:

- Scope of the GDPR;
- Legal basis and principles of the GDPR;
- Rights of the Data Subject;
- EU Legal Framework on Data (main Directives, Regulations and Proposals);
- Intellectual Property Rights;
- Relationship between Directives, National Laws and International Treaties.

For the Ethical issues, we understood that FAQs and Fact Sheets would not be the optimal format to share relevant information and the best practices on the matter. Instead, we proposed a brief **Guide** addressing some of the main resources on ethical issues related to research and Open Science.

Finally, considering that a substantial amount of this Deliverable addresses legal issues and/or is based on legal resources, some clarifications must be made:

Deliverable 3.6. (version 1)

- The legal resources used in this document are limited to those which were in effect at the date of its drafting. While there were important proposals for new directives/regulations at the time, they were not considered for these training materials;
- The main legal resources used in this document are EU Directives and Regulations. However, it should be noted that matters concerning specific fields, like copyright, are nationally regulated and, even though there is some harmonisation throughout the EU, national law must be considered. Your organization practices may be subject to national laws, sectoral regulation and other obligations set forth in contracts;
- Therefore, this material should be considered for general informatory purposes only. It must not be interpreted as legal advice in any circumstance and should not be used as basis for any decision regarding legal and ethical issues. For legal advice and advice on ethics, you should contact the competent offices inside your organization (eg legal office and ethics committee).

2 Personal Data Protection

EU legislation, namely the Regulation EU 2016/679 on the protection of natural persons about the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (hereinafter referred to as “GDPR”)¹ as well as other relevant directives, like the E-Privacy Directive (Directive 2002/58/EC), and the applicable laws, opinions and guidelines issued by the Supervisory Authorities, set up rules and mechanisms to ensure strong protection to personal data and counteract their unlawful and purposeless processing. The GDPR is directly legally applicable, i.e. it does not require implementing legislation at the national level, within the European Economic Area (EEA).

The GDPR ensures rights to data subjects but also imposes duties on natural and legal persons, public authorities, or other bodies (data controllers) while determining how to process personal data. Despite the attempt of harmonisation, the GDPR allows Member States to enact more stringent restrictions as in the case of certain categories of data such as health and genetic data.

Considering the centrality of the GDPR to the EU Legal Framework on Personal Data Protection, the following sections will provide an FAQ and multiple Fact Sheets on some of the main aspects of the GDPR that may be helpful to the beneficiaries of the trainings carried out using this material.

2.1 Fact Sheets

Slides 3 to 6 of the document provided in the appendix of this document and also in editable format in the Zenodo record (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7991444>)

¹ Regulation (Eu) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), OJEU 4.5.2016, L.119/1.

GDPR applies to personal data:

Arts 2 and 3, GDPR

GDPR, art. 3 Territorial scope

1. This Regulation applies to the processing of personal data in the context of the activities of an establishment of a controller or a processor in the Union, regardless of whether the processing takes place in the Union or not.
2. This Regulation applies to the processing of personal data of data subjects who are in the Union by a controller or processor not established in the Union, where the processing activities are related to: (a) the offering of goods or services, irrespective of whether a payment of the data subject is required, to such data subjects in the Union; or (b) the monitoring of their behaviour as far as their behaviour takes place within the Union.
3. This Regulation applies to the processing of personal data by a controller not established in the Union, but in a place where Member State law applies by virtue of public international law.

Scope of the GDPR (material and territorial scopes)

GDPR, art. 2 Material scope

1. This Regulation applies to the processing of personal data wholly or partly by automated means and to the processing other than by automated means of personal data which form part of a filing system or are intended to form part of a filing system.
2. This Regulation does not apply to the processing of personal data: (a) in the course of an activity which falls outside the scope of Union law; (b) by the Member States when carrying out activities which fall within the scope of Chapter 2 of Title V of the TEU; (c) by a natural person in the course of a purely personal or household activity; (d) by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, including the safeguarding against and the prevention of threats to public security.

Author: Valentina Colcelli and Sabrina Brizioli

Applicable Restrictions (art 23(1) and (2), GDPR)

Union or Member State law to which the data controller or processor is subject may restrict by way of a legislative measure the scope of the obligations and rights [...] when such a restriction **respects the essence of the fundamental rights and freedoms and is a necessary and proportionate measure in a democratic society to safeguard:**

- national security;
- defence;
- public security;
- the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, including the safeguarding against and the prevention of threats to public security;
- other important objectives of general public interest of the Union or of a Member State, in particular an important economic or financial interest of the Union or of a Member State, including monetary, budgetary and taxation matters, public health and social security;
- the protection of judicial independence and judicial proceedings;
- the prevention, investigation, detection and prosecution of breaches of ethics for regulated professions;
- a monitoring, inspection or regulatory function connected, even occasionally, to the exercise of official authority in [selected] cases;
- the protection of the data subject or the rights and freedoms of others;
- the enforcement of civil law claims.

In particular, any legislative measure referred [above] shall contain specific provisions at least, where relevant, as to:

- the purposes of the processing or categories of processing;
- the categories of personal data;
- the scope of the restrictions introduced;
- the safeguards to prevent abuse or unlawful access or transfer;
- the specification of the controller or categories of controllers;
- the storage periods and the applicable safeguards taking into account the nature, scope and purposes of the processing or categories of processing;
- the risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects; and
- the right of data subjects to be informed about the restriction, unless that may be prejudicial to the purpose of the restriction.

Author: Valentina Colcelli and Sabrina Brizioli

'Processing shall be lawful only if and to the extent that at least one of the following applies' (art 6(1)):

Legal Bases

- Consent**
 - 'the data subject has given consent to the processing of his or her personal data for one or more specific purposes'
- Performance of a contract**
 - 'processing is necessary for the performance of a contract to which the data subject is party or in order to take steps at the request of the data subject prior to entering into a contract'
- Compliance with a legal obligation**
 - 'processing is necessary for compliance with a legal obligation to which the controller is subject'
- Protection of vital interests**
 - 'processing is necessary in order to protect the vital interests of the data subject or of another natural person'
- Public interest**
 - 'processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller'
- Legitimate interest**
 - 'processing is necessary for the purposes of the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party, except where such interests are overridden by the interests or fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject which require protection of personal data, in particular where the data subject is a child.'

Author: Luca Schirru

2.2 FAQ

What is the GDPR?

The General Data Protection Regulation “lays down rules relating to the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and rules relating to the free movement of personal data.” (art. 1(1) GDPR);

What does “processing” encompass?

“Processing”, under the GDPR, encompasses “any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction;” (art. 4(2) GDPR).

What is “personal data”? (for GDPR purposes)

“[A]ny information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’)” (art. 4(1) GDPR).

What does “identifiable” means?

In order to be considered “identifiable” for the purposes of the regulation, a natural person may be “identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person” (art. 4(1) GDPR)

Does all kinds of personal data require the same treatment?

No. There are specific kinds of data that require special attention, as is the case of

personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation shall be prohibited. (GDPR, art. 9 (1)).

Another important type of data that deserves special treatment is children's personal data, as provided in the Recital 38 of the GDPR:

Children merit specific protection with regard to their personal data, as they may be less aware of the risks, consequences and safeguards concerned and their rights in relation to the processing of personal data. Such specific protection should, in particular, apply to the use of personal data of children for the purposes of marketing or creating personality or user profiles and the collection of personal data with regard to children when using services offered directly to a child. The consent of the holder of parental responsibility should not be necessary in the context of preventive or counselling services offered directly to a child.

Is informed consent always necessary?

Informed and free consent may be necessary for legitimate processing of personal data, since it is one of the possible legal bases for processing personal data under the GDPR. According to the GDPR, informed consent must be free, specific, informative and unambiguous and, therefore, cannot be presumed.

Are there any specific considerations for processing data for Research Purposes?

Yes. For example, art. 89 of the GDPR provides information on "safeguards and derogations relating to processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes",

which addresses, among other things, derogation of the right of access by the data subject, the right to rectification, and the right to object.

What are the main aspects of processing personal data to consider in research?

When it comes to the GDPR, multiple aspects should be taken into account when research activities encompass the processing of personal data, including but not limited to: the data subject identified or identifiable, the involvement of targeted groups (e.g., volunteers, workers, teenagers or children, vulnerable adults, local communities), the categories of data processed, and the kind of processing (e.g. secondary processing).

What kind of security measures must be employed?

Some technical and organisational security measures must be applied to facilitated the data flow towards the European Union. This is furthermore important in those cases in which a project consortium receives data for further processing. Partners of a consortium should have a legitimate interest in transmitting personal data and the flow of data for purposes other than those for which they were initially collected, which should be allowed if the activities are compatible with the scope for which the data and information were initially collected.

What is new under the GDPR in the approach to personal data?

The GDPR requires data controllers and processors to be responsible, to take responsibility for the processing activities, and to be compliant to principles and adequate safeguards. For this, the GDPR introduced the accountability principle, which is rooted in the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, specifically in art. 8 (protection of personal data).

What does accountability mean?

Pursuant to art. 5 of the GDPR, the controller shall be responsible for, and be able to demonstrate compliance with, the principles relating to the processing of personal data. This practically implies putting in place reliable

and effective measures and records to demonstrate compliance with data protection rules.

How to be responsible and compliant to GDPR according to the accountability principle?

Being compliant with the accountability principle is not a theoretical activity. Responsibility should be achieved by being proactive and able to organize effective data protection measures. Compliance essentially requires the ability to provide evidence that significant steps to protect personal data have been taken. Both responsibility and compliance, which are at the core of accountability, are pivotal to create a culture of commitment to data protection.

Does the GDPR provide indications to articulate an accountable approach to data?

Yes it does. Some relevant provisions of the GDPR can serve as an “accountable road map” to the processing of personal data:

- Recitals 39 and 83, arts. 24(1) and 32, GDPR: Ensuring security measures are in place;
- Recital 78 and art. 24(2), GDPR: Implementing data protection policies where appropriate;
- Recital 78 GDPR and art. 25, GDPR: Adopting data protection by design and by default;
- Recital 81 and art. 28, GDPR: Formalizing appropriate contracts with processors and sub-processors
- Recitals 42 and 82 and arts. 7(1), 30, and 33(5), GDPR: Maintaining appropriate documentation of processing activities;
- Recitals 85–88 GDPR arts. 33–34, GDPR: Recording and reporting data breaches;
- Recitals 84 and 89–95 GDPR and arts. 35–36: Carrying out data protection impact assessments (DPIAs) where required by the type of processing in particular using new technologies, and taking into account the nature, scope, context and purposes of the processing;
- Recital 97 and art. 37–39, GDPR: Assigning a data protection officer (DPO) where required;
- Recitals 98 and 100 and art. 40–43, GDPR: Adopting codes of conduct and certification schemes where appropriate.

3 Intellectual Property Rights and other non-personal data.

3.1 Fact Sheets

Slides 1 and 2 of the document available at: [Open files WP3 infographs.pptx - ONLYOFFICE \(skills4eosc.eu\)](https://skills4eosc.eu/Open_files_WP3_infographs.pptx)

3.2 FAQ

3.2.1 Intellectual Property (general)

Can I use third-party material (images, text, data, video etc) in my works (training materials, books, articles, etc)?

It depends. In addition to data that may be protected under the GDPR or regulated under other Directives/Regulations/Laws (eg 'research data' under the Open Data Directive and IoT data under the Data Act Proposal), some materials like photographs, videos, text, databases and information deemed as secrets can be protected by Intellectual Property Rights, which substantially limit the authorized uses without previous and express authorization of the rightsholder.

What is encompassed under the Intellectual Property Rights "umbrella"?

According to the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO, 2020, 3),
 'IP is often divided into two main categories: Industrial property includes patents for inventions, industrial designs, trademarks and geographical indications. Copyright and related rights cover literary, artistic and scientific works, including performances and broadcasts.'

A brief description of the scope of protection of these different IP rights is below:

<i>IPR</i>	<i>Description</i>
Patents	"An invention can be defined as a product or process that offers a new way of doing something, or a new technical solution to a problem. To qualify for patent protection, an

	<p>invention must be of some practical use and must offer something new which is not part of the existing body of knowledge in the relevant technical field (what lawyers call the prior art). But these requirements of <i>utility</i> and <i>novelty</i> are not enough; the invention must also involve an inventive step – something non-obvious that could not just have been deduced by someone with average knowledge of the technical field. Furthermore, the invention must not fall under non-patentable subject matter.” (WIPO, 2020, 5) (emphasis added)</p>
Trademarks	<p>“A trademark is a sign capable of distinguishing the goods or services of one enterprise from those of other enterprises.[...] All sorts of signs may be used as trademarks – words, letters, numbers, symbols, colors, pictures, three-dimensional signs such as shapes and packaging, holograms, sounds, even tastes and smells. To be eligible for registration, the basic principle is that a trademark must be distinctive, so it cannot just be a generic description of the product or service. Nor can it be identical (or very similar) to a trademark already registered or used for that type of product or service.” (WIPO, 2020, 12-13) (emphasis added)</p>
Industrial Designs	<p>“Industrial design rights cover those elements of a product that are aesthetic or ornamental – the way it looks and feels. [...] Industrial designs are applied to a wide variety of industrial products and handmade goods: cars, telephones, computers, packaging and containers, technical and medical instruments, watches, jewelry, electrical appliances, textile designs, and many other types of goods.” (WIPO, 2020, 8) (emphasis added)</p>
Geographical Indications	<p>“A geographical indication is a sign used on products that have a specific geographical origin and possess qualities or a reputation that are due to that origin. [...] There are different laws protecting geographical indications and different systems of recognition in different countries, so international law is developing ways to strengthen protection across national boundaries. ” (WIPO, 2020, 16) (emphasis added)</p>
Copyright and related rights	<p>“Copyright, or authors’ right, is a legal term used to describe the rights that creators have in their literary, artistic and scientific works. Copyright covers an enormous range of works – not just books, music, paintings, sculpture and films, but also computer programs, databases, advertisements, maps and technical drawings, among other things. There are also rights</p>

related to the copyright of the creators that protect the interests of those closely associated with copyrighted works, including performers, broadcasters and producers of sound recordings." (WIPO, 2020, 20) (emphasis added)

Source: designed with information extracted from WIPO (2020).

On building of training and educational material, as well as leading training sessions, which IPR(s) should be subject to further consideration?

Considering that training and educational material often reproduces excerpts of articles and books, images and/or audiovisual material, and may generate content that is protected under copyright and related rights, these are usually in the center of the discussion. However, it is advisable that the use of trademarks, commercial signs and information that could be deemed as secret should be carried out carefully. Finally, it is also important to notice that the releasing technical information on patentable inventions may eventually impede its owner of applying for patent protection, due to the lack of novelty.

3.2.2 Copyright

How the legal framework on copyright operates in the EU?

EU directives form the basis of intellectual property law and, therefore, copyright in the EU. They provide a framework for national laws that govern the protection and enforcement of IPRs in each member state. While ‘a "regulation" is a binding legislative act [and] must be applied in its entirety across the EU’, ‘a "directive" is a legislative act that sets out a goal that all EU countries must achieve [and] it is up to the individual countries to devise their own laws on how to reach these goals’.² It should be noted that matters concerning specific fields, like copyright, are nationally regulated and, even though there is some harmonisation throughout the EU, national law must be considered. A central concern regarding copyright in the EU is harmonisation, which is the process of aligning national laws with EU

² European Union, ‘Types of legislation’ <https://european-union.europa.eu/institutions-law-budget/law/types-legislation_en> accessed 14 Apr 2023. See also TFEU, art 288.

directives and international treaties to ensure consistency and coherence across different legal systems.

Which are the main copyright-related directives in the EU?

As it can be seen from the list below, there are several Directives and Regulations that are part of what is known as the “EU Copyright Law”:³

- i. Directive 93/83/EEC on the coordination of certain rules concerning copyright and rights related to copyright applicable to satellite broadcasting and cable retransmission;
- ii. Directive 96/9/EC on the legal protection of databases;
- iii. Directive 2001/84/EC on the resale right for the benefit of the author of an original work of art;
- iv. Directive 2001/29/EC on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society;
- v. Directive 2004/48/EC on the enforcement of intellectual property rights;
- vi. Directive 2006/115/EC on rental right and lending right and on certain rights related to copyright in the field of intellectual property;
- vii. Directive 2006/116/EC on the term of protection of copyright and certain related rights;
- viii. Directive 2009/24/EC on the legal protection of computer programs;
- ix. Directive 2011/77/EU on the term of protection of copyright and certain related rights amending the previous Term Directive;
- x. Directive 2012/28/EU on certain permitted uses of orphan works;
- xi. Directive 2014/26/EU on collective management of copyright and related rights and multi-territorial licensing of rights in musical works for online use in the internal market;
- xii. Directive 2017/1564/EU on certain permitted uses of certain works and other subject matter protected by copyright and related rights for the benefit of persons who are blind, visually impaired or otherwise print-disabled;

³ European Commission, ‘The EU copyright legislation’ <<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/copyright-legislation>>

- xiii. Regulation 2017/1563/EU on the cross-border exchange between the Union and third countries of accessible format copies of certain works and other subject matter protected by copyright and related rights for the benefit of persons who are blind, visually impaired or otherwise print-disabled;
- xiv. Regulation 2017/1128/EU on cross-border portability of online content services in the internal market;
- xv. Directive 2019/789/EU on the exercise of copyright and related rights applicable to certain online transmissions of broadcasting organisations and retransmissions of television and radio programme;
- xvi. Directive 2019/790/EU on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market.

However, it should be remembered that **copyright is a matter to be addressed by national law**, and the directives are just a part of the legal framework on copyright that should be considered in the EU. More information on the functioning of the Copyright Legal Framework in the EU can be found in the Fact Sheet '*IPRs: Relationship between Directives, National Laws and International Treaties*'.

And what is needed for a work to be protected under copyright in the EU?⁴

The protection of works under EU copyright law requires the satisfaction of criteria concerning originality and expression. EU copyright law has relied on case law to refine and clarify the scope of protection. In the EU, a work must be **original** in order to qualify for copyright protection. The notion of originality is harmonized in the EU through the case law of the CJEU.⁵ Following the landmark decision of the CJEU in *Infopaq*⁶ and its subsequent case law,⁷ a work is considered “original” if it resembles the “author’s own

⁴ Authored by Emircan Karabuga and reviewed by Luca Schirru.

⁵ Tatiana-Eleni Synodinou, Philippe Jougoux, Christiana Markou and Thalia Prastitou-Merdi, 'EU Internet Law in the Digital Single Market' (Springer Cham 2021), 183.

⁶ Case C 5/08 *Infopaq International A/S v Danske Dagblades Forening* [2009] ECLI:EU:C:2009:465.

⁷ Case C-393/09 *Bezpečnostní softwarová asociace – Svaz softwarové ochrany v Ministerstvo kultury* [2011] ECLI:EU:C:2010:816, para 45; Case C-145/10 *Eva-Maria Painer v*

intellectual creation”.⁸ Hence, “originality” can be said to arise from the unique elements embodied in a work that resembles the author’s personality or personal touch.⁹ Similarly, in the Football Dataco case, the CJEU affirmed that copyright protection for databases only applies if they are original in the selection or arrangement of their contents.¹⁰

Article 2 of the InfoSoc Directive excludes certain types of works from copyright protection, including ideas, procedures, methods of operation, and mathematical concepts. This exclusion acknowledges the **idea/expression dichotomy** and ensures that copyright law does not impede creativity or innovation in these fields. Under the idea/expression dichotomy, copyright protection only applies to the specific expression of an idea, rather than the underlying idea itself. This implies that an author is not entitled to exclusive rights over an idea or concept, but solely over its manifestation in tangible form.¹¹

In conclusion, the principles of the idea/expression dichotomy, case law, and statutory exclusions serve to demarcate the limits of copyright protection in the EU, by balancing the interests of creators, users, and society at large.

Under copyright, which kind of “uses” are deemed as exclusive in the EU legal framework?

Just as an example, the InfoSoc Directive¹² regulates the Reproduction right (art 2), the right of Communication to the Public (art 3), the right of Making Available (art 3), and the Distribution right (art 4). One issue that is highlighted in the literature¹³, is the wide scope of the Reproduction Right as

Standard Verlags GmbH [2012] ECLI:EU:C:2013:138, para 87.

⁸ Tatiana-Eleni Synodinou, Philippe Jougoux, Christiana Markou and Thalia Prastitou-Merdi, ‘EU Internet Law in the Digital Single Market’ (Springer Cham 2021), 183.

⁹ *ibid.*

¹⁰ Case C-604/10 Football Dataco Ltd v Yahoo! UK Ltd & Others [2012] ECR I-619.

¹¹ Lipton and Torremans, *Copyright Law*, 3rd edn, 2019, p 47.

¹² Directive 2001/29/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2001 on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society [2001] OJ L167.

¹³ T Margoni & M Kretschmer, *A Deeper Look into the EU Text and Data Mining Exceptions: Harmonisation, Data Ownership, and the Future of Technology* (2022) 71(8) GRUR International 689.

it can be seen in art. 2 of the InfoSoc, as it would encompass ‘the exclusive right to authorise or prohibit direct or indirect, temporary or permanent reproduction by any means and in any form, in whole or in part’. Other legal texts, as the Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works also specifically address the right of Adaptation (art 12), the right of Translation (art 8), among others.

This means that I need to ask for authorisation for using any third-party copyrighted material?

Not necessarily. Apart from the uses authorized under a license, it is also possible to use copyrighted works that are in the (i) public domain or (ii) that the use is comprised under the Limitations and Exceptions (L&Es). Also, remember that the material that you are intending to use may not be covered by copyright OR that it may be covered by other exclusive rights, as is the case of the SGDR, which may require additional, and different, authorizations.

In practice, what are the effects of a work being in public domain?

In summary, ‘being in the public domain’ means that the exclusive economic rights on that copyrighted work have expired and, therefore, everyone can use that work, even for commercial purposes. However, it should be noted that the moral rights of the author should continue to be respected.

It is enough to check the InfoSoc, the CDSM or any specific directive to confirm whether a use is under a L&E?¹⁴

While the InfoSoc Directive and the CDSM Directive provide a legal framework for lawful exceptions or limitations to copyright (L&E) in EU copyright law, determining whether a particular use is covered by an L&E requires more than a mere reference to these directives. This is because the specific conditions and limitations for each L&E are established in the national copyright laws of each EU member state.

Moreover, the determination of whether a particular use falls within the scope of an L&E may be influenced by other international treaties, directives or agreements that are relevant to the particular work or use in question. Consequently, a comprehensive analysis of the relevant legal provisions,

¹⁴ Authored by Emircan Karabuga and reviewed by Luca Schirru.

including both the applicable EU directives and national laws, is required in order to ascertain the applicability of L&E to a given use.

Thus, while the InfoSoc and CDSM Directives, for example, form an important part of the legal framework for copyright protection and L&E in the EU, a more nuanced and detailed analysis is necessary to determine whether a specific use falls under an L&E. This entails a thorough examination of the relevant national copyright laws and case law, as well as other applicable international legal instruments.

If it is not in public domain and the use is not covered by a L&E, it means that I’m not allowed to use it?

If (i) it is protected under copyrights, (ii) it is not in the public domain, (iii) the use is not covered by L&Es and (iv) was not licensed by the rightholder, then there is a high risk of copyright infringement.

What if I don’t know who the author/owner is?

In these cases, there is a possibility of the work being an ‘orphan work’. In the EU, the permitted uses of orphan works are regulated under national laws, as they pertain to the copyright field. In the regional level, the Directive 2012/28/EU (‘Orphan Works Directive’) addresses these works. The rules provided in the directive refer to a specific set of institutions, i.e., “publicly accessible libraries, educational establishments and museums, as well as by archives, film or audio heritage institutions and public-service broadcasting organisations, established in the Member States” and such uses shall be carried out “in order to achieve aims related to their public-interest missions” (Orphan Works Directive, art 1(1)).

What are orphan works?

Orphan works (or phonograms) are those which “none of the rightholders in that work or phonogram is identified or, even if one or more of them is identified, none is located despite a *diligent search* for the rightholders having been carried out and recorded” (Orphan Works Directive, art. 2(1)).

What an investigation should have to be considered as a diligent search?

A diligent search is an essential step to legitimize the use of an orphan work, because it would allow to properly recognize the work/phonogram as an orphan work/phonogram, and must “be carried out prior to the use of the

work or phonogram.” (Orphan Works Directive, art 3(1)). The diligent search, according to art. 3(1) of Orphan Works Directive, shall consider “the appropriate sources for the category of works and other protected subject-matter in question”. The exact sources where such search should be carried out shall be determined by the national law (Orphan Works Directive, art 3(2)), in addition to those listed in the Annex of the Orphan Works Directive.

Important: further information on the uses of Orphan Works/Phonograms may be found in the applicable national laws, the Directive 2012/28 and further applicable regulation.

If it is not copyrighted work, it means that I can use the data?

Not necessarily. As mentioned before, copyright is not the only exclusive right that may require further steps and caution before using third-parties’ content. Other exclusive rights may arise, for example, sui generis database rights (item 3.2.3.) and specific rules applicable to trade secrets (item 3.2.4.)

3.2.2.1 Copyright and Open Science

What is Open Science?

As defined in the UNESCO Recommendation, Open Science is “an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, to increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community”.¹⁵

Mendez and others (2020, 22) propose that Open Science it’s not an end in itself, but a means to a larger effort, where “Open Science must ultimately be embedded as part of a larger more systemic effort to foster all practices and processes that enable the creation, contribution, discovery and reuse of research knowledge more reliably, effectively and equitably”.

¹⁵ UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (2021) <<https://en.unesco.org/science-sustainable-future/open-science/recommendation>>

The broad scope of what is encompassed by 'Open Science' it is well depicted by the taxonomy found in the FOSTER Portal, listing "Open Access", "Open Data", "Open Reproducible Research", "Open Science Evaluation", "Open Science Policies" and "Open Science Tools" as elements of OS.¹⁶

Which are some of the most common copyright-related issues on Open Science?

One important aspect of Open Science is Open Access. According to the definition provided by UNESCO:

"Open access (OA) means **free access to information and unrestricted use of electronic resources** for everyone. Any kind of digital content can be OA, from texts and data to software, audio, video, and multimedia. While most of these are related to text only, a growing number are integrating text with images, data, and executable code. OA can also apply to non-scholarly content, like music, movies, and novels. A publication is considered in Open access if:

- its content is universally and freely accessible, at no cost to the reader, via the Internet or otherwise;
- the author or copyright owner irrevocably grants to all users, for an unlimited period, the right to use, copy, or distribute the article, on condition that proper attribution is given;
- it is deposited, immediately, in full and in a suitable electronic form, in at least one widely and internationally recognized open access repository committed to open access."¹⁷

Open Access, today, cannot be analysed without considering the whole commercial scientific publishing sector dynamics. One example is the current business model that combines OA publishing with substantial Article

¹⁶ Foster Open Science Website (n.d.) <<https://www.fosteropenscience.eu/resources>>.

¹⁷ UNESCO, 'What is Open Access?' (n.d.) <<https://en.unesco.org/open-access/what-open-access>>

Processing Charge (APC),¹⁸ that can ultimately promote inequality if not properly addressed.¹⁹

Regarding the business models in scientific publishing, what are Green, Bronze, Gold, Hybrid and Diamond OA?

<i>Type of OA</i>	<i>Description</i>
Bronze OA	“In the Bronze OA model the journal is officially subscription-only and no author fee is charged for OA publishing. However, the publisher can choose, for a brief period, to release a publication free to read on their website but without an open license like Creative Commons (perhaps for marketing purposes or in response to health emergencies such as the COVID-19 pandemic). Bronze OA is therefore not truly OA since the publisher can close off free access at any time, whereas genuinely OA publications have an open license that ensures the publication to be permanently and freely accessible with clear agreements about sharing and reuse.”
Green OA	“Green OA, also known as self-archiving or open archiving, means that you archive a digital copy (usually the accepted version) of your publication in an online repository. This archival copy is made available to the public – often after an embargo period.”
Gold OA	“Gold OA, a.k.a. open publishing, means that the publisher makes the published version of your work immediately and freely available to the public. The cost of publishing is either carried by the author (who pays an author fee) or by a third party (Diamond OA), but never by the reader.[...] There are different types of Gold OA, such as Full OA and Hybrid OA.”
Full OA	“In a Full OA journal, opposed to a Hybrid OA journal, all the articles are

¹⁸ “Article processing charges (or APCs) are fees to be paid by the author (author fees) to publish his/her research article in immediate OA (Gold OA). The cost of an APC varies greatly depending on the publisher: it can be determined cost-effectively (non-profit OA) or it can include a profit margin (for-profit OA). Keep in mind that there are also OA journals that do not charge APCs, allowing you to make your article available in OA without having to pay for it.”. KU Leuven, ‘Glossary’ (What is Open Science, n.d.) accessed 12 Apr 2023 <<https://www.kuleuven.be/open-science/what-is-open-science/scholarly-publishing-and-open-access/glossary#APC>>

¹⁹ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Mendez, E., Lawrence, R., Progress on open science: towards a shared research knowledge system: final report of the open science policy platform, Brussels: Publications Office 2020, p 18; ALLEA Statement on Open Access Publication Under “Big Deals” and the New Copyright Rules. 2022

	published in immediate OA, without embargo.”
Hybrid OA	“A Hybrid OA journal, opposed to a Full OA journal, is a subscription-based journal that offers authors the option to publish their individual article in OA by payment of an author fee. The articles that are published in OA are freely available to the readers, but the journal as such is still published behind a paywall.”
Diamond OA	“Diamond OA is a Gold Open Access publication system in which there is neither cost to the reader (no subscription cost) nor to the author(s) (no author fees). This is made possible because the publishing infrastructure is subsidized by a third party (e.g. a funding agency or a consortium of university libraries). Diamond OA is often (not not always) determined by a non-profit mission. Therefore, the KU Leuven Fund for Fair OA sponsors various Diamond OA initiatives.”

Designed with information extracted from KU Leuven, ‘Glossary’ (What is Open Science, n.d.) accessed 12 Apr 2023 <<https://www.kuleuven.be/open-science/what-is-open-science/scholarly-publishing-and-open-access/glossary>>

What is “double-dipping”?

Double-dipping is a term usually employed when while addressing the Hybrid OA:

This model is called “double dipping” as the journal makes a double profit: on the one hand, the author pays a fee to get his/her article published in OA, and on the other hand, the library/reader pays a subscription fee to have access to the other articles in that same journal.²⁰

Besides the licensing frameworks addressed in 3.2.2.2, are there other copyright-related tools that may be employed to promote Open Science?

Important measures are being adopted both in the legislative and organizational levels, for example: (i) Rights Retention Strategies (administrative/organizational level) and (ii) Secondary Publication Rights (legislative level).²¹

²⁰ KU Leuven, ‘Glossary’ (What is Open Science, n.d.) accessed 12 Apr 2023 <<https://www.kuleuven.be/open-science/what-is-open-science/scholarly-publishing-and-open-access/glossary>>

²¹ See, eg, European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Angelopoulos, C., *Study on EU copyright and related rights and access to and reuse of scientific publications, including open access : exceptions and limitations, rights retention*

What are Secondary Publication Rights (SPRs)?

A Secondary Publication Right (SPR) can be understood as “a right for the author of a scientific publication to make it available online for free following a given embargo period”.²² Legislative measures concerning SPRs are being introduced in countries like Austria, Germany, The Netherlands, and Belgium. In Belgium, for example, even if the author has assigned his rights to a publisher, they can make the manuscript freely available in twelve months (for humanities and social sciences) or six months (for other sciences) after the first publication, in case the article was a product of a public-funded research (Belgium Code of Economic Law, art XI. 196 2 §).

Are SPRs present in all EU countries?

No. The fact that SPRs are still largely nationally driven is an aspect that from the point of view of a European research space is seen as harmful legal fragmentation. Nevertheless, the interest in having this kind of publication openly accessible is not simply a national priority but is part a broader vision for a European research space as exemplified by the Commission Recommendation 2018/790 on access to and preservation of scientific information.²³

What are Rights Retention Strategies?

On the organizational level, and in order to promote Open Access, initiatives like those under the cOAlition S are proposing Rights Retention Strategies (RRS),²⁴ which requires changes in different nodes of the dynamics between funding organizations, researchers and publishers, and that can be summarized in the text below, part of the Plan S guidance:

Where possible, cOAlition S members will ensure by way of funding contracts or agreements that the authors or their institutions retain copyright as well as the rights that are

strategies and the secondary publication right, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/891665>.

²² Angelopoulos, 2022, 4.

²³ Commission Recommendation 2018/790 on access to and preservation of scientific information [2018] OJ L 134/12

²⁴ Coalition S (n.d.) Accelerating the transition to full and immediate Open Access to scientific publications <https://www.coalition-s.org/wp-content/uploads/PlanS_Principles_and_Implementation_310519.pdf>

necessary to make a version (either the VoR, the AAM or both) immediately available under an open license. To this end, cOAlition S will develop or adopt a model 'License to Publish' for their grantees. (cOAlition S, n.d., 2)

The recent [Self-Archiving Policy](#) implemented by the University of Cambridge and the [Plan S Rights Retention Strategy](#) are examples of these measures.

3.2.2.2 Licensing

What are open licenses?

An open license can be defined as “one which grants permission to access, re-use and redistribute a work with few or no restrictions”²⁵ depending on the chosen license.

For the purposes of this training material, we shall use the “Creative Commons” open licenses as the main examples of this kind of licenses. And this is not because they are the only existing open licenses, but they are the most adopted licensing framework, largely used in EC-related documents as part of the Commission Decision of 12 December 2011 on the reuse of Commission documents (2011/833/EU).

What are Creative Commons Licenses? ²⁶

Contrary to the default rule of "All Rights Reserved" under copyright law, which requires permission for (almost) every use of a work, Creative Commons (CC) aims to create an environment in which "Some Rights Reserved" or even "No Rights Reserved" become standard.²⁷ CC provides several standard-form licenses, which allow creators of literary, musical, and audiovisual works to authorize wide dissemination and transformative use of their works without relinquishing their copyrights.²⁸ This means that when authors grant broad licenses to the public on a royalty-free basis through

²⁵ Open Knowledge Foundation, 'Open Definition: Defining Open in Open Data, Open Content and Open Knowledge' (n.d.) <<https://opendefinition.org/guide/>>.

²⁶ Authored by Emircan Karabuga and reviewed by Luca Schirru.

²⁷ Lucie Guibault, 'Open Content Licensing: From Theory to Practice – An Introduction.' In *Open Content Licensing: From Theory to Practice*, edited by Lucie Guibault and Christina Angelopoulos (Amsterdam University Press 2011) 7, 8.

²⁸ *ibid.*

open licensing, it does not mean that they have abandoned their copyrights or that the works are not copyright-protected.²⁹ Instead, they have opted not to exercise certain exclusive rights, such as the right to prevent others from using their work, the right to control its use, and the right to monetize their work.³⁰ However, CC has also developed the CC0 dedication, which enables authors to renounce all their rights to their work with respect to copyright and related matters.³¹

The CC licenses are the only ‘open’ licenses?

No. There are multiple ‘open’ licenses, some of the specific to a particular set of works, as is the case of the FLOSS (Free, Libre and Open Source Software) licenses. Just among these particular category of licenses, there are multiple types of license, as it can be seen from this [list](#) made available by the GNU Operating System – Free Software Foundation.³²

Being licensed under a CC license is the same as being in public domain?

No. According to the Creative Commons:

‘CC licenses are copyright licenses, and depend on the existence of copyright to work. CC licenses are legal tools that creators and other rights holders can use to offer certain usage rights to the public, while reserving other rights. Those who want to make their work available to the public for limited kinds of uses while preserving their copyright may want to consider using CC licenses. Others who want to reserve all of their rights under copyright law should not use CC licenses.’³³

What if the national law goes against the terms of the CC license?

²⁹ Till Kreutzer, ‘User-Related Assets and Drawbacks of Open Content Licensing’ In Open Content Licensing: From Theory to Practice, edited by Lucie Guibault and Christina Angelopoulos (Amsterdam University Press 2011) 107, 112.

³⁰ *ibid.*

³¹ Marie-Christine Janssens, Arina Gorbatyuk, Sonsoles Pajares Rivas, ‘Copyright Issues on the use of images on the Internet’ In Research Handbook on Intellectual Property and Cultural Heritage (Edward Elgar 2022) 191, 204.

³² GNU Operation System, ‘Various Licenses and Comments about Them’ (06 Apr 2023) <<https://www.gnu.org/licenses/license-list.html>>

³³ Creative Commons, ‘Frequently Asked Questions’ (13 Jan 2023) <<https://creativecommons.org/faq/#is-creative-commons-against-copyright>>

The CC licenses were built to work in the international level as much as possible. However, there are times that their terms may conflict with the national copyright law. And this may happen in cases where the Limitations and Exceptions of a copyright law authorize some use that would be allowed under a copyright license. The current CC-BY License 4.0. Address this issue in Sec 2(a)(2):

Section 2(a)(2): Exceptions and Limitations. For the avoidance of doubt, where Exceptions and Limitations apply to Your use, this Public License does not apply, and You do not need to comply with its terms and conditions.

Do CC licenses cover other IP rights or personality rights?

No. Generally, CC licenses are meant to deal with copyrights and, in the case of the version 4.0, sui generis database rights (SGDR). As stated by the Creative Commons, '[t]he license may not give you all of the permissions necessary for your intended use. For example, other rights such as publicity, privacy, or moral rights may limit how you use the material.'³⁴ Also, section 2(b)(1)(2) of the CC-BY 4.0. Provides that:

'Moral rights, such as the right of integrity, are not licensed under this Public License, nor are publicity, privacy, and/or other similar personality rights; however, to the extent possible, the Licensor waives and/or agrees not to assert any such rights held by the Licensor to the limited extent necessary to allow You to exercise the Licensed Rights, but not otherwise. Patent and trademark rights are not licensed under this Public License.'

3.2.3 Sui Generis Database Rights (SGDR)

What are the sui generis database rights?

Despite being in the same Directive as the copyright protection to databases, these rights are different in their scope and justification.

³⁴ Creative Commons, 'Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)' <
<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>>

These rights apply only when it is possible to show that “there has been qualitatively and/or quantitatively a substantial investment in either the obtaining, verification or presentation of the contents to prevent extraction and/or re-utilization of the whole or of a substantial part [...] of the contents of that database” (art 7(1) of the Database Directive).

What do “extraction” and “re-utilization” mean?

According to art. 7 (2)(a)(b) of the Database Directive, these terms shall have the following meanings:

(a) ‘extraction’ shall mean the permanent or temporary transfer of all or a substantial part of the contents of a database to another medium by any means or in any form;

(b) ‘re-utilization’ shall mean any form of making available to the public all or a substantial part of the contents of a database by the distribution of copies, by renting, by on-line or other forms of transmission. The first sale of a copy of a database within the Community by the rightholder or with his consent shall exhaust the right to control resale of that copy within the Community;

If one of the legal requirements is “substantial investment”, what is usually considered as such?

To precise whether there was substantial investment, both in the qualitative and/or quantitative aspect, is a matter to be dealt with in a case-by-case basis. However, case law in the EU and the Database Directive itself may provide some guidance. By “investment”, Recital 40 of the Database directive, provides that it may “consist in the deployment of financial resources and/or the expending of time, effort and energy”.

As an example of what can or can’t be considered as “substantial investment”, Recital 19 of the Database directive provides that “as a rule, the compilation of several recordings of musical performances on a CD [...] does not represent a substantial enough investment to be eligible under the sui generis right”.

In the case law, cases like the *Fixtures Marketing*³⁵ and the *British Horseracing Board*³⁶ give us some additional information. In the *British Horseracing Board*, it is clear that the aforementioned investment should not address the creation of the material but the collection:

[...] the expression ‘investment in ... the obtaining ... of the contents’ of a database must, [...] be understood to refer to the resources used to seek out existing independent materials and collect them in the database, and not to the resources used for the creation as such of independent materials.³⁷

The contributions brought by the *Fixtures Marketing* case are twofold. The first one concerns the “qualitative” and “quantitative” terms: “[t]he quantitative assessment refers to quantifiable resources and the qualitative assessment to efforts which cannot be quantified, such as intellectual effort or energy [...]”³⁸. The second one concerns the analysis, in that case of the investments in the verification and presentation of contents:

The expression ‘investment in ... the ... **verification** ... of the contents’ of a database must be understood to refer to the resources used, with a view to ensuring the reliability of the information contained in that database, to monitor the accuracy of the materials collected when the database was created and during its operation. The expression ‘investment in ... the ... **presentation** of the contents’ of the database concerns, for its part, the resources used for the purpose of giving the database its function of processing information, that is to say those used for the systematic or methodical arrangement of the materials contained in that database and the organisation of their individual accessibility³⁹. [emphasis added]

³⁵ Case C-338/02 *Fixtures Marketing Ltd v Svenska Spel AB* [2004] ECR I-10497

³⁶ Case C-203/02 *The British Horseracing Board Ltd and Others v William Hill Organization Ltd* [2004] ECR I-10415

³⁷ Case C-203/02 *The British Horseracing Board Ltd and Others v William Hill Organization Ltd* [2004] ECR I-10415, para 31.

³⁸ Case C-338/02 *Fixtures Marketing Ltd v Svenska Spel AB* [2004] ECR I-10497, para 28.

³⁹ Case C-338/02 *Fixtures Marketing Ltd v Svenska Spel AB* [2004] ECR I-10497, para 27.

How the copyright protection to databases is different from the *sui generis* database rights?

There are multiple differences between both rights, including but not limited to the (i) requirements for protection, (ii) exceptions to the exclusive rights, and (iii) term of protection..

Requirements:

Copyright protection: copyright protection shall be granted to databases when “by reason of the selection or arrangement of their contents, constitute the author’s own intellectual creation shall be protected as such by copyright” (art 3(1) of the Database Directive).

SGDR protection: regardless of the originality in the selection or arrangement of their contents, databases may be protected under the SGDR if they show that “there has been qualitatively and/or quantitatively a substantial investment in either the obtaining, verification or presentation of the contents to prevent extraction and/or re-utilization of the whole or of a substantial part [...] of the contents of that database.” (art 7(1) of the Database Directive)

Exceptions to the exclusive rights:

Not only the granted rights, but also the exceptions to these exclusive rights change. Art. 6 of the Database Directive provides some optional limitations that may be added to the national law concerning copyright protected databases (Additional limitations and exceptions that can be found in other Directives/Treaties may apply). On the other hand, art. 9 of the Database Directive provides the specific exceptions to the *sui generis* right.

Term of protection:

While the SGDR term of protection generally “shall expire fifteen years from the first of January of the year following the date of completion” (art 10 of the Database Directive), the copyright protection on original databases shall be, with some exceptions provided by law, the whole life of the author plus 70 years after his death (art 1 of the Term Directive).⁴⁰

Why it is important to make such distinction?

⁴⁰ Directive 2006/116/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 on the term of protection of copyright and certain related rights [2006] OJ L 372/12.

Not only because the scope, duration and requirements are different, but because we can have cases where both rights coexists. Consider a database made of photographs, which the content selection was original and the obtaining of the content required substantial investment.

In this case, we would have at least three layers of rights under the non-personal data legal framework:

1. *First layer*: photographs can be protected by copyright individually, regardless of being part of the database;
2. *Second layer*: copyright protection to the database itself because of its original selection;
3. *Third layer*: SGDR protection to the database because of the substantial investment employed in the content selection.

It is not uncommon that these three layers of rights are owned by different rightsholders with different interests and ways of licensing (if needed) their rights.

3.2.4 Trade Secrets

What is considered as a trade secret?

Being a trade secret is not necessarily connected to any characteristic of the information itself, but to measures that are employed in relation to it. In order to be considered “trade secret”, the information must meet the following criteria:

- (a) it is secret in the sense that it is not, as a body or in the precise configuration and assembly of its components, generally known among or readily accessible to persons within the circles that normally deal with the kind of information in question;
- (b) it has commercial value because it is secret;
- (c) it has been subject to reasonable steps under the circumstances, by the person lawfully in control of the information, to keep it secret;⁴¹

⁴¹ Art 2(1) of the Trade Secrets Directive. Directive (EU) 2016/943 of the European Parliament

On the regional level, the protection conferred to Trade Secrets is regulated by Directive (EU) 2016/943 ('Trade Secrets Directive'). As commented when addressing other IP rights, other related directives, international treaties and the national laws on the subject matter should be considered, since national laws can be even more restrictive than the rules set out in the Trade Secrets Directive.⁴²

What is the scope of the Trade Secrets Directive?

In order to properly address the scope of the Trade Secrets Directive, it is necessary to address the difference between lawful and unlawful acquisition, use and disclosure of trade secrets. This is because, the Directive 'lays down rules on the protection against the unlawful acquisition, use and disclosure of trade secrets.' (art 1(1) of the Trade Secrets Directive).

When the acquisition, use and disclosure of Trade Secrets is considered unlawful?

Below, we provide lists of practices that are considered lawful and unlawful acquisition, use and disclosure under the Trade Secrets Directive. As it was seen in the questions related to copyright, the rights provided in the Trade Secrets Directive also have exceptions, which can also be considered as legitimate uses, and are listed in the "lawful acquisition, use and disclosure" column.

Lawful acquisition, use and disclosure	Unlawful acquisition, use and disclosure
'independent discovery or creation' (art 3(1)(a) of the Trade Secrets Directive)	'unauthorised access to, appropriation of, or copying of any documents, objects,

and of the Council of 8 June 2016 on the protection of undisclosed know-how and business information (trade secrets) against their unlawful acquisition, use and disclosure [2016] OJ L 157/1.

⁴² According to the Trade Secrets Directive, in its art. 1(1): '1. This Directive lays down rules on the protection against the unlawful acquisition, use and disclosure of trade secrets. Member States may, in compliance with the provisions of the TFEU, provide for more far-reaching protection against the unlawful acquisition, use or disclosure of trade secrets than that required by this Directive [...]'.

	materials, substances or electronic files, lawfully under the control of the trade secret holder, containing the trade secret or from which the trade secret can be deduced' (art 4(2)(a) of the Trade Secrets Directive)
'observation, study, disassembly or testing of a product or object that has been made available to the public or that is lawfully in the possession of the acquirer of the information who is free from any legally valid duty to limit the acquisition of the trade secret' (art 3(1)(b) of the Trade Secrets Directive)	'any other conduct which, under the circumstances, is considered contrary to honest commercial practices' (art 4(2)(b) of the Trade Secrets Directive)
'exercise of the right of workers or workers' representatives to information and consultation in accordance with Union law and national laws and practices' (art 3(1)(c) of the Trade Secrets Directive)	'whenever carried out, without the consent of the trade secret holder, by a person who is found to meet any of the following conditions: (a) having acquired the trade secret unlawfully; (b) being in breach of a confidentiality agreement or any other duty not to disclose the trade secret; (c) being in breach of a contractual or any other duty to limit the use of the trade secret' (art 4(3) of the Trade Secrets Directive)
'any other practice which, under the circumstances, is in conformity with honest commercial practices' (art 3(1)(d) of the Trade Secrets Directive)	'whenever a person, at the time of the acquisition, use or disclosure, knew or ought, under the circumstances, to have known that the trade secret had been obtained directly or indirectly from another person who was using or disclosing the trade secret unlawfully within the meaning [of art 4(3) above]' (art 4(4) of the Trade Secrets Directive)
'required or allowed by Union or national law' (art 3(2) of the Trade Secrets Directive)	'The production, offering or placing on the market of infringing goods, or the importation, export or storage of infringing

	<p>goods for those purposes, shall also be considered an unlawful use of a trade secret where the person carrying out such activities knew, or ought, under the circumstances, to have known that the trade secret was used unlawfully within the meaning [of art 4(3) above]' (art 4(5) of the Trade Secrets Directive)</p>
<p>Exceptions provided in Art. 5</p> <p>'Member States shall ensure that an application for the measures, procedures and remedies provided for in this Directive is dismissed where the alleged acquisition, use or disclosure of the trade secret was carried out in any of the following cases:</p> <p>(a) for exercising the right to freedom of expression and information as set out in the Charter, including respect for the freedom and pluralism of the media;</p> <p>(b) for revealing misconduct, wrongdoing or illegal activity, provided that the respondent acted for the purpose of protecting the general public interest;</p> <p>(c) disclosure by workers to their representatives as part of the legitimate exercise by those representatives of their functions in accordance with Union or national law, provided that such disclosure was necessary for that exercise;</p> <p>(d) for the purpose of protecting a legitimate interest recognised by Union or national law' (emphasis added)</p>	<p>-</p>

3.2.5 Non-personal data and Public Sector Bodies

3.2.5.1 Open Data Directive

Are there any specific concerns if the data I intend to use is the product of a research that was publicly funded?

On this matter, we should pay special attention to two different scenarios. The first one is the regulation of data under the Open Data Directive, and the other one specifically refers to data (and deliverables) from EU-funded projects.

What is the Open Data Directive?

The Open Data Directive⁴³ aims to “promote the use of open data and stimulate innovation in products and services” by setting “minimum rules governing the re-use and the practical arrangements for facilitating the re-use of” certain data.⁴⁴

Which kind of data is covered by the ODD?

The data covered by ODD are the following:

- (a) existing documents held by public sector bodies of the Member States;
- (b) existing documents held by public undertakings that are:
 - (i) active in the areas defined in Directive 2014/25/EU;
 - (ii) acting as public service operators pursuant to Article 2 of Regulation (EC) No 1370/2007;
 - (iii) acting as air carriers fulfilling public service obligations pursuant to Article 16 of Regulation (EC) No 1008/2008; or
 - (iv) acting as Community shipowners fulfilling public service obligations pursuant to Article 4 of Regulation (EEC) No 3577/92;
- (c) **research data** pursuant to the conditions set out in Article 10. (emphasis added)

What is understood as ‘research data’ under the ODD?

⁴³ Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information [2019] OJ L 172/56 (ODD – Open Data Directive).

⁴⁴ ODD, art 1(1).

Concerning the ‘research data’ referred in the ODD, these should be understood as “documents in a digital form, other than scientific publications, which are collected or produced in the course of scientific research activities and are used as evidence in the research process, or are commonly accepted in the research community as necessary to validate research findings and results”.⁴⁵ It is clear from the art 2(1)(c) that the ODD does not apply to “documents for which third parties hold intellectual property rights”.

What are the uses that should be allowed for research data under the ODD?

Regarding the uses allowed under the ODD for research data, and considering the scope of this Directive, countries must provide a legal framework that should allow the (re)use of research data “for commercial or non-commercial purposes” if:

- they are publicly funded and
- researchers, research performing organisations or research funding organisations have already made them publicly available through an institutional or subject-based repository.⁴⁶

The uses allowed shall be carried out “in accordance with Chapters III and IV” of the ODD and additional factors must be taken into account, as is the case of “legitimate commercial interests, knowledge transfer activities and pre-existing intellectual property rights”.⁴⁷

It is important to highlight that, as a Directive, the ODD is not directly enforceable in the EU Member States, and a thorough analysis of the national policies and actions on Open Science should be carried out in order to ensure the legitimacy of the intended uses for a selected material.⁴⁸

⁴⁵ ODD, art 2(9)

⁴⁶ ODD, art 10(2).

⁴⁷ ODD, art 10(2).

⁴⁸ According to art 10(1) of the ODD, “1. Member States shall support the availability of research data by adopting national policies and relevant actions aiming at making publicly funded research data openly available (‘open access policies’), following the principle of ‘open by default’ and compatible with the FAIR principles. In that context, concerns relating to intellectual property rights, personal data protection and confidentiality, security and legitimate commercial interests, shall be taken into account in accordance with the principle of ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary’. Those open access policies shall be addressed to research performing organisations and research funding organisations.”.

What are High-Value Datasets?

According to art 2(10) of the ODD

means documents the re-use of which is associated with important benefits for society, the environment and the economy, in particular because of their suitability for the creation of value-added services, applications and new, high-quality and decent jobs, and of the number of potential beneficiaries of the value-added services and applications based on those datasets.

According to the Annex I of the ODD, the current thematic categories for the high-value datasets are the following: (i) Geospatial; (ii) Earth observation and environment; (iii) Meteorological; (iv) Statistics; (v) Companies and company ownership; (vi) Mobility. “Such specific high-value datasets shall be”:

- (a) available free of charge, subject to paragraphs 3, 4 and 5;
- (b) machine readable;
- (c) provided via APIs; and
- (d) provided as a bulk download, where relevant.⁴⁹

The Commission shall adopt implementing acts (i) “laying down a list of specific high-value datasets belonging to the categories set out in Annex I” and that (ii) “may specify the arrangements for the publication and re-use of high-value datasets”, which (iii) “shall be compatible with open standard licences.”⁵⁰

What happens if the research data or some kind of data that would be covered by the rules of the ODD are subject to IP rights owned by third parties?

Art 1(2)(c) of the ODD is clear when it affirms that the Directive does not apply to “documents for which third parties hold intellectual property rights”. Therefore, considering that “certain categories of data, such as commercially confidential data, data that are subject to statistical confidentiality and data protected by intellectual property rights of third parties, including trade secrets and personal data, in public databases are often not made available,

⁴⁹ ODD, art 14 (1).

⁵⁰ ODD, art 14 (1).

not even for research or innovative activities in the public interest”,⁵¹ comments must be made on the Data Governance Act that, among other objectives, aims to provide “conditions for the re-use, within the Union, of certain categories of data held by public sector bodies”.⁵²

3.2.5.2 Data Governance Act⁵³

What is the nature of data covered by the DGA?

For the purposes of this document, and focusing on the data that is held by PSIs and could be (re)used, the main categories are the following:

data held by public sector bodies which are protected on grounds of:

- (a) commercial confidentiality, including business, professional and company secrets;
- (b) statistical confidentiality;
- (c) the protection of intellectual property rights of third parties;
- or
- (d) the protection of personal data, insofar as such data fall outside the scope of Directive (EU) 2019/1024.

Does the DGA interfere in the ownership or exercise of the IPRs by Public Sector Bodies?

No. The DGA “should neither affect the existence or ownership of intellectual property rights of public sector bodies nor limit the exercise of those rights in any way”.⁵⁴ Therefore, rules contained therein should not go against the national law, EU law on IPRs and international treaties on the subject matters (eg Berne Convention, TRIPS and the WCT).⁵⁵

⁵¹ Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (2022) OJ L 152/1 (Data Governance Act), rec 6.

⁵² DGA, Art 1(1)(a).

⁵³ On the matter, see Baloup, J., E Bayamlioglu, A Benmayor, C Ducuing, L Dutkiewicz, T Lalova, Y Miadzvetskaya, and B Peeters, White Paper on the Data Governance Act (2021) CiTiP Working Paper <<https://www.law.kuleuven.be/citip/blog/citip-white-paper-on-the-data-governance-act/>>.

⁵⁴ DGA, rec 17.

⁵⁵ Id

The main idea under the DGA is that PSIs exercise their IP rights (including the SGDR) in a way to facilitate re-use.⁵⁶

Then, which are some of the main contributions from the DGA when it comes to IPRs?

One of them is the establishment of the European Data Innovation Board, which has amongst its tasks the duty to

to advise and assist the Commission with regard to developing consistent guidelines on how to best protect, in the context of this Regulation, commercially sensitive non-personal data, in particular trade secrets, but also non-personal data representing content protected by intellectual property rights from unlawful access that risks intellectual property theft or industrial espionage⁵⁷

The DGA also provides a set of conditions for (re)use of protected data that may be adopted by Public Sector Bodies and which encompasses, among others, that the access and (re)use of data is carried within a ‘secure processing environment’.⁵⁸ For the purposes of the DGA,

“secure processing environment” means the physical or virtual environment and organisational means to ensure compliance with Union law, such as Regulation (EU) 2016/679, in particular with regard to data subjects’ rights, intellectual property rights, and commercial and statistical confidentiality, integrity and accessibility, as well as with applicable national law, and to allow the entity providing the secure processing environment to determine and supervise all data processing actions, including the display, storage, download and export of data and the calculation of derivative data through computational algorithms.⁵⁹

⁵⁶ DGA, recs 17 and 18.

⁵⁷ DGA, art 30(d)

⁵⁸ DGA, art 5(3)(b)(c).

⁵⁹ DGA, art 2(20).

3.2.5.3 Data under EU-funded projects

What if the data I intend to use were generated by EU-funded projects?

Depending on the grant agreement, there may be mandatory practices related to Open Science, and therefore, Open Access to be carried out by the beneficiary(ies). As an example, Projects funded under the Horizon Europe Program must comply with the obligations provided in the Grant Agreement and, therefore, with the “open access prior obligation”.⁶⁰

To provide further illustration, and when it comes to scientific publications, according to the rules contained on Annex 5 of the Annotated Grant Agreement (Draft Version) and concerning Art 17 of such Agreement,

The beneficiaries must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results. In particular, they must ensure that:

- at the latest at the time of publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication, is deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications
- immediate open access is provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the licence may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g. CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND) and
- information is given via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication. Beneficiaries (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the open access requirements⁶¹

⁶⁰ Commission, ‘What is the “open access prior obligation”?’ (Funding & Tender Opportunities, 2018c) <<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/faq/22153?type=0,1;categories=;tenders=;programme=null;keyword=;freeTextSearchKeyword=%20prior%20obligation;matchWholeText=true;period=null;status=0;sortQuery=publicationDate;faqListKey=faqSearchTablePageState>>

⁶¹ Commission, EU Grants AGA – Annotated Grant Agreement: EU Funding Programmes 2021-2027 (v.1 Draft, 01 Apr 2023), <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding->

The document also provides further duties regarding metadata and the data involved in the research.

[tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf](#) accessed 06 apr 2023.

4 Ethics in research and open science

Addressing ethical issues is always a complex undertaking. One of the reasons is that ethical issues may vary according to the field of research (eg research with human cells may raise different ethical issues than a research using artificial intelligence systems). Another one is relating to the fact that ethical issues and, therefore, guidelines/codes of conduct can be far more dynamic than legal texts. There are multiple, and different, normative theories and principles related to each one of them.⁶² Vedder (2019, 2) also highlights that “[...] ethics – to the degree that it is not incorporated in the law – does not enjoy the same status as to its legitimacy and authority as the law does”. And, finally, by “ethics” one can have very different understandings of what is comprised:

‘Ethics’ may refer to (A) the concrete feelings, opinions, and arguments in moral matters, existing in the minds and the hearts of people and materializing in their actions, policies etc. It may, however, also refer to (B) the academic discipline that methodically reflects on moral matters, sometimes also referred to as moral philosophy or philosophical ethics. In the latter sense, ethics may be (B1) an *empirical undertaking*, mainly describing what people think and feel, how they reason and judge concerning good or bad intentions, actions, lives etc. – in sum, a branch of philosophy overlapping to a large degree with social sciences – or it may be (B2) *critically normative*, by providing proposals for intentions, actions and ways of life, or their assessment.⁶³

Similar to what is seen in the sections that address legal issues and personal and non-personal data, it is clear that there is no way to properly address all ethical issues that may concern research practices: this would be far from optimal both because the document would easily be obsolete in a few months and because that there will be practically impossible to address all the ethical issues in all research fields (see, eg, [Declaration of Helsinki](#) and

⁶² For example, deontological, utilitarian and communitarian theories. Anton Vedder, ‘Mind the gap. Managing the expectations of legal scholars turning to ethics for help where the law does not yet provide answers’ In: Centre for IT & IP Law (ed.) Rethinking IT and IP Law. Celebrating 30 Years CiTiP Cambridge/Antwerp: Intersentia, 2019, pp. 305-312 <https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3450544>.

⁶³ Vedder (2019) 2.

the [UNESCO Universal Declaration on Bioethics and Human Rights](#))⁶⁴ and environments (eg [EAG Report “Towards a digital ethics”](#)),⁶⁵ with the employment of specific technologies (eg the [Ethical Guidelines for Trustworthy AI](#))⁶⁶, from all the multiple and different approaches to what is “ethics”.

Considering the above, we will present some of the main documents that address ethical issues in research, focusing on those that, in some way, tackle OS-related issues. They will be briefly described, and a set of additional resources about them and their relationship with OS will be provided. Even within this narrower approach, the documents addressed here are just a part of a whole framework of guidelines, codes of conduct and other instruments that could be categorized under different ways, for example, according to their scope, form, target group, and content.⁶⁷

4.1 FAIR Principles

The FAIR principles are a set of guidelines that can be employed to make data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. These principles can be better described using the Box2 provided in Wilkinson and others (2016):

FAIR Principles	Description
Findable	“F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent

⁶⁴ World Medical Association (WMA), ‘WMA Declaration of Helsinki – Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Subjects’ (6 Sep 2022) <<https://www.wma.net/policies-post/wma-declaration-of-helsinki-ethical-principles-for-medical-research-involving-human-subjects/>>. UNESCO, ‘Universal Declaration on Bioethics and Human Rights’ (19 Oct 2005) <<https://www.unesco.org/en/legal-affairs/universal-declaration-bioethics-and-human-rights?hub=66535>>.

⁶⁵ European Data Protection Supervisor, Ethics Advisory Group, JP Burgess et al., ‘Towards a digital ethics’ (2018) <https://edps.europa.eu/sites/edp/files/publication/18-01-25_eag_report_en.pdf>.

⁶⁶ European Commission, High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, ‘Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI’ (2018) <<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>>.

⁶⁷ Sutrop, Parder and Juurik (2019)

	<p>identifier</p> <p>F2. data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)</p> <p>F3. metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes</p> <p>F4. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.”</p>
Accessible	<p>“A1. (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol</p> <p>A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable</p> <p>A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary</p> <p>A2. metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available.”</p>
Interoperable	<p>“I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.</p> <p>I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles</p> <p>I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data”</p>
Reusable	<p>“R1. meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes</p> <p>R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license</p> <p>R1.2. (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance</p> <p>R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards”.</p>

Source: Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Sci Data 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>, Box 2.

There is a substantial amount of relevant resources on the FAIR principles: projects, deliverables, scientific articles, courses, etc. For the purpose of this document, the article [“The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship”](#) and related materials, initiatives aiming to translate the principles into practice like [GO FAIR](#) and [FAIRsFAIR](#), and EU

publications like “[Turning FAIR into reality](#)”⁶⁸ and “[Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science](#)”⁶⁹ are relevant resources on the matter.

4.2 Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)

“RRI” stands for Responsible Research and Innovation and “aims to create a society in which R&I work towards sustainable, ethically acceptable, and socially desirable outcomes, addressing several agendas needed for a fair and just society”.⁷⁰ Under the [RRI Tools](#) and [ORBIT](#) projects, the six main aspects of RRI would be “Ethics, Science Education, Gender Equality, Open Access, Governance and Public Engagement.”⁷¹

On the ethical part of it, it is worth highlighting that

When it comes to Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), the core ethical endeavour is to achieve its integration across the entire research and innovation (R&I) process. This process can be roughly divided into four phases: policy making and agenda setting, funding call formulation, project definition and proposal writing, and project execution and evaluation. Integrating ethics into these phases requires continuous orientation, reflection and deliberation on the decisions, actions and values at stake.⁷²

Many documents and projects address RRI practices. Some of them are listed below:

- ORBIT RRI: <https://www.orbit-rri.org/>

⁶⁸ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Turning FAIR into reality : final report and action plan from the European Commission expert group on FAIR data*, Publications Office, 2018, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/1524>

⁶⁹ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Manola, N., Lazzeri, E., Barker, M., et al., *Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science : report from the EOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group*, Manola, N. (editor), Lazzeri, E. (editor), Barker, M. (editor), Kuchma, I. (editor), Gaillard, V. (editor), Stoy, L. (editor), Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/59065>

⁷⁰ RRI Tools, ‘Training on RRI’ <<https://rri-tools.eu/training/about>>

⁷¹ ORBIT, ‘The Keys of Responsible Research and Innovation’ (n.d.) <<https://www.orbit-rri.org/resources/keys-of-rri/>>

⁷² RRI Tools, ‘How to promote research integrity’ <<https://rri-tools.eu/how-to-pa-ethics#menu-anchor-id2-content>>

- RRI Tools: <https://rri-tools.eu/ethics>
- WBC-RRI – Responsible research and Innovation in the Western Balkans: <https://wbc-rri.net/>
- “Responsible research and innovation (RRI), science and technology” report: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/ee9bacdf-fdad-46eb-8cd8-32879e310191/language-en/format-PDF/source-283914549>.

4.3 European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity

Codes/guidelines on ethics vary across different fields of expertise. In research, for example, the [European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) is one of the main resources. If personal data is processed, some best practices related to ethics may also apply (see, eg, [here](#)).

The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity is a code of conduct made available by the All European Academies (ALLEA) with the main objectives of “[serving] the research community as a framework for self-regulation” and to help realise the “basic responsibility of the research community[, which is] is to formulate the principles of research, to define the criteria for proper research behaviour, to maximise the quality and robustness of research, and to respond adequately to threats to, or violations of, research integrity”.⁷³

In the document, good research practices are described in multiple contexts, these being: “Research Environment; Training, Supervision and Mentoring; Research Procedures; Safeguards; Data Practices and Management; Collaborative Working; Publication and Dissemination; Reviewing, Evaluating and Editing”.⁷⁴

From the analysis of the good practices recommended in different contexts, it is possible to clearly identify OS-related practices in almost all the contexts mentioned above, as it can be seen from the table below:

Context	OS-related good practices
Research Environment	“Research institutions and organisations reward open and reproducible practices in hiring and promotion of researchers.”

⁷³ ALLEA (2017, 3).

⁷⁴ ALLEA (2017, 5).

Research Procedures	“Researchers publish results and interpretations of research in an open, honest, transparent and accurate manner, and respect confidentiality of data or findings when legitimately required to do so.”
Data Practices and Management	“Researchers, research institutions and organisations ensure access to data is as open as possible, as closed as necessary, and where appropriate in line with the FAIR Principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable) for data management.”
Collaborative Working	“All partners in research collaborations agree at the outset on the goals of the research and on the process for communicating their research as transparently and openly as possible.”
Publication and Dissemination	“Authors ensure that their work is made available to colleagues in a timely, open, transparent, and accurate manner, unless otherwise agreed, and are honest in their communication to the general public and in traditional and social media.”
Reviewing, Evaluating and Editing	“Researchers review and evaluate submissions for publication, funding, appointment, promotion or reward in a transparent and justifiable manner”

Source: ALLEA (2017, 5-8)

The document also provides fundamental principles of research integrity:

- **Reliability** in ensuring the quality of research, reflected in the design, the methodology, the analysis and the use of resources.
- **Honesty** in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting and communicating research in a transparent, fair, full and unbiased way.
- **Respect** for colleagues, research participants, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage and the environment.
- **Accountability** for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organisation, for training, supervision and mentoring, and for its wider impacts.⁷⁵

⁷⁵ ALLEA (2017, 4)

5 References

ALLEA Statement on Open Access Publication Under “Big Deals” and the New Copyright Rules. 2022

Anton Vedder, ‘Mind the gap. Managing the expectations of legal scholars turning to ethics for help where the law does not yet provide answers’ In: Centre for IT & IP Law (ed.) Rethinking IT and IP Law. Celebrating 30 Years CiTiP Cambridge/Antwerp: Intersentia, 2019, pp. 305-312 <https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3450544>

Baloup, J., E Bayamlioglu, A Benmayor, C Ducuing, L Dutkiewicz, T Lalova, Y Miadzvetskaya, and B Peeters, White Paper on the Data Governance Act (2021) CiTiP Working Paper <<https://www.law.kuleuven.be/citip/blog/citip-white-paper-on-the-data-governance-act/>>.

Case C 5/08 Infopaq International A/S v Danske Dagblades Forening [2009] ECLI:EU:C:2009:465

Case C-145/10 Eva-Maria Painer v Standard Verlags GmbH [2012] ECLI:EU:C:2013:138

Case C-203/02 The British Horseracing Board Ltd and Others v William Hill Organization Ltd [2004] ECR I-10415

Case C-338/02 Fixtures Marketing Ltd v Svenska Spel AB [2004] ECR I-10497

Case C-393/09 Bezpečnostní softwarová asociace – Svaz softwarové ochrany v Ministerstvo kultury [2011] ECLI:EU:C:2010:816

Case C-604/10 Football Dataco Ltd v Yahoo! UK Ltd & Others [2012] ECR I-619

Coalition S (n.d.) Accelerating the transition to full and immediate Open Access to scientific publications <https://www.coalition-s.org/wp-content/uploads/PlanS_Principles_and_Implementation_310519.pdf>

Commission Recommendation 2018/790 on access to and preservation of scientific information [2018] OJ L 134/12

Commission, ‘What is the “open access prior obligation”?’ (Funding & Tender Opportunities, 2018c) <<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/faq/22153?type=0,1;categories=;tenders=;programme=null;keyword=;freeTextSearchKeyword=%20prior%20obligation;matchWholeText=true;period=null;status=0;sortQuery=publicationDate;faqListKey=faqSearchTablePageState>>

Commission, EU Grants AGA – Annotated Grant Agreement: EU Funding Programmes 2021-2027 (v.1 Draft, 01 Apr 2023), https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf accessed 06 apr 2023

Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, A European strategy for data (the European Data Strategy), COM/2020/66 final [2020]

Creative Commons, 'Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)' <<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>>

Creative Commons, 'Frequently Asked Questions' (13 Jan 2023) <https://creativecommons.org/faq/#is-creative-commons-against-copyright>

Directive (EU) 2016/943 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 8 June 2016 on the protection of undisclosed know-how and business information (trade secrets) against their unlawful acquisition, use and disclosure [2016] OJ L 157/1.

Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information [2019] OJ L 172/56 (ODD – Open Data Directive).

Directive (EU) 2019/790 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market and amending Directives 96/9/EC and 2001/29/EC (Directive on Copyright in the Digital Single Market) [2019], OJ L 130

Directive 2006/116/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 on the term of protection of copyright and certain related rights [2006] OJ L 372/12.

European Commission, 'The EU copyright legislation' <<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/copyright-legislation>>

European Commission, Directorate-General for Communication, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Responsible research and innovation (RRI), science and technology : report, Publications Office, 2013, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/45726>

European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Angelopoulos, C., Study on EU copyright and related rights and access to and reuse of scientific publications, including open access : exceptions and

limitations, rights retention strategies and the secondary publication right, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/891665>

European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Manola, N., Lazzeri, E., Barker, M., et al., Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science : report from the EOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group, Manola, N. (editor), Lazzeri, E. (editor), Barker, M. (editor), Kuchma, I. (editor), Gaillard, V. (editor), Stoy, L. (editor), Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/59065>

European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Mendez, E., Lawrence, R., Progress on open science: towards a shared research knowledge system: final report of the open science policy platform, Brussels: Publications Office 2020

European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Turning FAIR into reality : final report and action plan from the European Commission expert group on FAIR data, Publications Office, 2018, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/1524>

European Commission, High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 'Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI' (2018) <<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>>

European Data Protection Supervisor, Ethics Advisory Group, JP Burgess et al., 'Towards a digital ethics' (2018) <https://edps.europa.eu/sites/edp/files/publication/18-01-25_eag_report_en.pdf>

European Union, 'Types of legislation' <https://european-union.europa.eu/institutions-law-budget/law/types-legislation_en> accessed 14 Apr 2023.

European Union, Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (2012) OJ C 326/49.

'FAIRSFAR', 'The Project' <<https://www.fairsfair.eu/the-project>>.

Foster Open Science Website (n.d.) <<https://www.fosteropenscience.eu/resources>>.

GNU Operation System, 'Various Licenses and Comments about Them' (06 Apr 2023) <<https://www.gnu.org/licenses/license-list.html>>

'GO FAIR' <<https://www.go-fair.org/>>.

J Pila & P Torremans, 'European Intellectual Property Law' (OUP, 2edn, 2019) at 60.

KU Leuven, 'Glossary' (What is Open Science, n.d.) accessed 12 Apr 2023 <<https://www.kuleuven.be/open-science/what-is-open-science/scholarly-publishing-and-open-access/glossary>>

Lipton and Torremans, Copyright Law, 3rd edn, 2019

Lucie Guibault, 'Open Content Licensing: From Theory to Practice – An Introduction.' In Open Content Licensing: From Theory to Practice, edited by Lucie Guibault and Christina Angelopoulos (Amsterdam University Press 2011)

Marie-Christine Janssens, Arina Gorbatyuk, Sonsoles Pajares Rivas, 'Copyright Issues on the use of images on the Internet' In Research Handbook on Intellectual Property and Cultural Heritage (Edward Elgar 2022)

Open Knowledge Foundation, 'Open Definition: Defining Open in Open Data, Open Content and Open Knowledge' (n.d.) <<https://opendefinition.org/guide/>>.

'ORBIT RRI' <<https://www.orbit-rri.org/resources/keys-of-rri/>>

P Goldstein & P Bernt Hugenholtz, 'International Copyright: Principles, Law, and Practice (OUP 4edn 2019)

Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation or GDPR) [2016], OJ L 119/1

Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (2022) OJ L 152/1 (Data Governance Act)

'Responsible research and innovation in the Western Balkans (WBC-RRI)' <<https://wbc-rri.net/>>

'RRI Tools' <<https://rri-tools.eu/ethics>>

Sganga, Caterina, Gebreyesus, Netsanet Haile, van Wezel, Jos, Foggetti, Nadina, Amram, Denise, & Drago, Federico. (2022). EOSC-Pillar Legal Compliance Guidelines for Researchers: a Checklist (interactive digital version). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6327668>

Sutrop, M., Parder, ML., Juurik, M. (2020). Research Ethics Codes and Guidelines. In: Iphofen, R. (eds) Handbook of Research Ethics and Scientific Integrity. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-76040-7_2-1

Tatiana-Eleni Synodinou, Philippe Jougleux, Christiana Markou and Thalia Prastitou-Merdi, 'EU Internet Law in the Digital Single Market' (Springer Cham 2021)

T Margoni & M Kretschmer, A Deeper Look into the EU Text and Data Mining Exceptions: Harmonisation, Data Ownership, and the Future of Technology (2022) 71(8) GRUR International 689

Till Kreutzer, 'User-Related Assets and Drawbacks of Open Content Licensing' In Open Content Licensing: From Theory to Practice, edited by Lucie Guibault and Christina Angelopoulos (Amsterdam University Press 2011)

United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) Recommendation on Open Science (2021) <https://en.unesco.org/science-sustainable-future/open-science/recommendation>

UNESCO, 'Universal Declaration on Bioethics and Human Rights' (19 Oct 2005) <<https://www.unesco.org/en/legal-affairs/universal-declaration-bioethics-and-human-rights?hub=66535>>

UNESCO, 'What is Open Access?' (n.d.) <<https://en.unesco.org/open-access/what-open-access>>

Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Sci Data 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), 'What is Intellectual Property' (2020) <https://www.wipo.int/edocs/pubdocs/en/wipo_pub_450_2020.pdf>

World Medical Association (WMA), 'WMA Declaration of Helsinki – Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Subjects' (6 Sep 2022) <<https://www.wma.net/policies-post/wma-declaration-of-helsinki-ethical-principles-for-medical-research-involving-human-subjects/>>

6 Appendix

This appendix includes the infographs related to Deliverable 3.6. An editable version of the infographs is available in Zenodo record (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7991444>)

IPRs: Relationship between Directives, National Laws and International Treaties

Harmonization of IPRs: Harmonization is the process of aligning national laws with EU directives and international treaties to ensure consistency and coherence across different legal systems.

EU Law and the difference between EU Regulations and EU Directives: EU directives form the basis of intellectual property law in the EU. They provide a framework for national laws that govern the protection and enforcement of IPRs in each member state. While ‘a "regulation" is a binding legislative act [and] must be applied in its entirety across the EU’, ‘a "directive" is a legislative act that sets out a goal that all EU countries must achieve [and] it is up to the individual countries to devise their own laws on how to reach these goals.’¹ In practical terms, a relevant legal effect of it is that Regulations may “be invoked directly by individuals in proceedings before national courts – including vertical proceedings (against the state) and horizontal proceedings (against other individual.s) – as a source of individual rights and obligations” and “directives do not penetrate automatically and directly into the legal orders of Member States, and cannot be invoked before domestic courts in the manner of EU regulations”.²

International Treaties: International treaties establish minimum standards for the protection and enforcement of IPRs, and are relevant to understand the functioning of IPRs in the EU. While it is clear from art 216(2) from the TFEU that [international] “agreements concluded by the Union are binding upon the institutions of the Union and on its Member States”,³ the legal effects of each IP-related International Treaty must be further and individually analyzed. On the International Treaties relevant to IPR, Goldstein and Hugenholtz (2019, 60) explain that “all countries of the E.U. belong to the Berne Union, adhere to the Rome Convention, and, through membership in the WTO, are bound by the TRIPs Agreement. The E.U. and its member states have also ratified the WIPO treaties. As a consequence, the harmonized rules on copyright and neighboring rights of the E.U. tend to require member states to offer more, but not less, protection than is required by the relevant international treaties”.⁴

1 European Union, ‘Types of legislation’ <https://european-union.europa.eu/institutions-law-budget/law/types-legislation_en> accessed 14 Apr 2023. See also TFEU, art 288.
 2 J Pila & P Torremans, ‘European Intellectual Property Law’ (OUP, 2edn, 2019) at 60.
 3 TFEU, art 216(2) and 2 J Pila & P Torremans, ‘European Intellectual Property Law’ (OUP, 2edn, 2019) at 60-63.
 4 P Goldstein & P Bernt Hugenholtz, ‘International Copyright: Principles, Law, and Practice (OUP 4edn 2019), at 60 (footnotes omitted)

Important: The Directives and Regulations provided here are just a selection of the legal texts concerning intellectual property (IP) within the European Union (EU) framework.. Currently, the EU copyright legal framework comprises 13 Directives and 2 regulations. For more information on these Directives and Regulations, we recommend visiting the EC webpage on the EU Copyright Law: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/copyright-legislation>

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

Regulation (EU) 2016/679: 'This Regulation lays down rules relating to the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and rules relating to the free movement of personal data', and 'protects fundamental rights and freedoms of natural persons and in particular their right to the protection of personal data.' (GDPR, art. 1(1)(2))

Data Act (DA - proposal)

The proposed regulation aims to lay down: 'harmonised rules on making data generated by the use of a product or related service available to the user of that product or service, on the making data available by data holders to data recipients, and on the making data available by data holders to public sector bodies or Union institutions, agencies or bodies, where there is an exceptional need, for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest' (DA, art. 1(1))

Artificial Intelligence Act (AIA - proposal)

The proposed regulation aims to lay down: 'harmonised rules for the placing on the market, the putting into service and the use of artificial intelligence systems ('AI systems') in the Union; (a) prohibitions of certain artificial intelligence practices; (b) specific requirements for high-risk AI systems and obligations for operators of such systems; (c) harmonised transparency rules for AI systems intended to interact with natural persons, emotion recognition systems and biometric categorisation systems, and AI systems used to generate or manipulate image, audio or video content; (d) rules on market monitoring and surveillance.' (AIA, art. 1)

Digital Markets Act (DMA)

Regulation (EU) 2022/1925: 'The purpose of this Regulation is to contribute to the proper functioning of the internal market by laying down harmonised rules ensuring for all businesses, contestable and fair markets in the digital sector across the Union where gatekeepers are present, to the benefit of business users and end users.' (DMA, art. 1(1))

Digital Services Act (DSA)

Regulation (EU) 2022/2065: 'The aim of this Regulation is to contribute to the proper functioning of the internal market for intermediary services by setting out harmonised rules for a safe, predictable and trusted online environment that facilitates innovation and in which fundamental rights enshrined in the Charter, including the principle of consumer protection, are effectively protected.' (DSA, art. 1(1))

Open Data Directive (ODD)

Directive (EU) 2019/1024: 'In order to promote the use of open data and stimulate innovation in products and services, this Directive establishes a set of minimum rules governing the re-use and the practical arrangements for facilitating the re-use of certain kinds of data. (ODD, art. 1(1))

Data Governance Act (DGA)

Regulation (EU) 2022/868: 'This Regulation lays down: (a) conditions for the re-use, within the Union, of certain categories of data held by public sector bodies; (b) a notification and supervisory framework for the provision of data intermediation services; (c) a framework for voluntary registration of entities which collect and process data made available for altruistic purposes; and (d) a framework for the establishment of a European Data Innovation Board.'" (DGA, art. 1(1))

Regulation on a framework for the free flow of non-personal data in the European Union (FFNPD)

Regulation (EU) 2018/1807: 'This Regulation aims to ensure the free flow of data other than personal data within the Union by laying down rules relating to data localisation requirements, the availability of data to competent authorities and the porting of data for professional users.' (FFNPD, art. 1)

EU Legal Framework on Data

(main Directives, Regulations and Proposals)

Trade Secrets Directive

Directive (EU) 2016/943: 'This Directive lays down rules on the protection against the unlawful acquisition, use and disclosure of trade secrets.' (art.1(1))

CDSM Directive

Directive (EU) 2019/790: 'This Directive lays down rules which aim to harmonise further Union law applicable to copyright and related rights in the framework of the internal market, taking into account, in particular, digital and cross-border uses of protected content. It also lays down rules on exceptions and limitations to copyright and related rights, on the facilitation of licences, as well as rules which aim to ensure a well-functioning marketplace for the exploitation of works and other subject matter.' (art.1(1))

Term Directive

Directive 2006/116/EC on the term of protection of copyright and certain related rights.

InfoSoc Directive

Directive 2001/29/EC: 'This Directive concerns the legal protection of copyright and related rights in the framework of the internal market, with particular emphasis on the information society.' (art. 1(1)).

Directive on the legal protection of databases

Directive 96/9/EC: 'This Directive concerns the legal protection of databases in any form.' (art.1(1))

Directive on Orphan Works

Directive 2012/28/EU: 'This Directive concerns certain uses made of orphan works by publicly accessible libraries, educational establishments and museums, as broadcasting well as by archives, film or audio heritage institutions and public-service organisations, established in the Member States, in order to achieve aims related to their public-interest missions.' (art. 1 (1))

Directive on the legal protection of computer programs

Directive 2009/24/EC: 'In accordance with the provisions of this Directive, Member States shall protect computer programs, by copyright, as literary works within the meaning of the Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works.' (art. 1 (1))

Important: The Directives and Regulations provided here are just a selection of the legal texts concerning intellectual property (IP) within the European Union (EU) framework.. Currently, the EU copyright legal framework comprises 13 Directives and 2 regulations. For more information on these Directives and Regulations, we recommend visiting the EC webpage on the EU Copyright Law: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/copyright-legislation>

‘Processing shall be lawful only if and to the extent that at least one of the following applies’ (art 6(1)):

Consent

- ‘the data subject has given consent to the processing of his or her personal data for one or more specific purposes’

Performance of a contract

- ‘processing is necessary for the performance of a contract to which the data subject is party or in order to take steps at the request of the data subject prior to entering into a contract’

Compliance with a legal obligation

- ‘processing is necessary for compliance with a legal obligation to which the controller is subject’

Protection of vital interests

- ‘processing is necessary in order to protect the vital interests of the data subject or of another natural person’

Public interest

- ‘processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller’

Legitimate interest

- ‘processing is necessary for the purposes of the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party, except where such interests are overridden by the interests or fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject which require protection of personal data, in particular where the data subject is a child.’

Data protection authority

Data subject

Personal data

Data controller

Data processor(s)

Lawfulness, fairness and transparency

Purpose Limitation

Data minimisation

Accuracy

Storage limitation

Integrity and Confidentiality

Accountability

Personal data shall be 'processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject'

Personal data shall be 'collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes'

Personal data shall be 'adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed'

Personal data shall be 'accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date'

Personal data shall be 'kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed'

Personal data shall be 'processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures'

'The controller shall be responsible for, and be able to demonstrate compliance with' the previous items

Principles

GDPR applies to personal data:

Processed by a controller or processor in the EU

Of data subject in the EU for specified activities and the controller and processor are not established in the EU

In the context of the activities of an establishment of a controller or a processor in the EU, even if the processing is not in the EU

Which form part of a filing system or are intended to

Wholly or partly processed by automated means

Arts 2 and 3, GDPR

GDPR, art. 3 Territorial scope

1. This Regulation applies to the processing of personal data in the context of the activities of an establishment of a controller or a processor in the Union, regardless of whether the processing takes place in the Union or not.

2. This Regulation applies to the processing of personal data of data subjects who are in the Union by a controller or processor not established in the Union, where the processing activities are related to: (a) the offering of goods or services, irrespective of whether a payment of the data subject is required, to such data subjects in the Union; or (b) the monitoring of their behaviour as far as their behaviour takes place within the

Union. 3. This Regulation applies to the processing of personal data by a controller not established in the Union, but in a place where Member State law applies by virtue of public international law.

Scope of the GDPR (material and territorial scopes)

GDPR, art. 2 Material scope

1. This Regulation applies to the processing of personal data wholly or partly by automated means and to the processing other than by automated means of personal data which form part of a filing system or are intended to form part of a filing system.
2. This Regulation does not apply to the processing of personal data: (a) in the course of an activity which falls outside the scope of Union law; (b) by the Member States when carrying out activities which fall within the scope of Chapter 2 of Title V of the TEU; (c) by a natural person in the course of a purely personal or household activity; (d) by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, including the safeguarding against and the prevention of threats to public security.

Rights of the Data Subject

Transparent information, communication and modalities for the exercise of the rights of the Data Subject (art 12)

Right of access by the data subject (art 15)

Right to rectification (art 16)

Right to erasure ('right to be forgotten') (art 17)

Right to restriction of processing (art 18)

Right to data portability (art 20)

Right to object (art 21)

Applicable Restrictions (art 23(1) and (2), GDPR)

Union or Member State law to which the data controller or processor is subject may restrict by way of a legislative measure the scope of the obligations and rights [...] when such a restriction **respects the essence of the fundamental rights and freedoms and is a necessary and proportionate measure in a democratic society to safeguard:**

- national security;
- defence;
- public security;
- the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, including the safeguarding against and the prevention of threats to public security;
- other important objectives of general public interest of the Union or of a Member State, in particular an important economic or financial interest of the Union or of a Member State, including monetary, budgetary and taxation matters, public health and social security;
- the protection of judicial independence and judicial proceedings;
- the prevention, investigation, detection and prosecution of breaches of ethics for regulated professions;
- a monitoring, inspection or regulatory function connected, even occasionally, to the exercise of official authority in [selected] cases;
- the protection of the data subject or the rights and freedoms of others;
- the enforcement of civil law claims.

In particular, any legislative measure referred [above] shall contain specific provisions at least, where relevant, as to:

- the purposes of the processing or categories of processing;
- the categories of personal data;
- the scope of the restrictions introduced;
- the safeguards to prevent abuse or unlawful access or transfer;
- the specification of the controller or categories of controllers;
- the storage periods and the applicable safeguards taking into account the nature, scope and purposes of the processing or categories of processing;
- the risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects; and
- the right of data subjects to be informed about the restriction, unless that may be prejudicial to the purpose of the restriction.